

Abstract

The present study was undertaken in Yavatmal district of Vidarbha region. The district was selected purposively. The data pertained for the year 2022-23. The per hectare cost of cultivation of pre-seasonal sugarcane was Rs.237899.75/- and for suru sugarcane was Rs.228992.22/- The highest input – output ratio at C₂ was recorded for pre-seasonal sugarcane i.e. 1:1.99 and for suru sugarcane was 1:1.85. Farmers growing pre-seasonal sugarcane obtained higher output per hectare than that of suru sugarcane.

Keyword; sugarcane, pre-seasonal, suru sugarcane, Cost of cultivation

Introduction

The agricultural sector plays a crucial role in the Indian economy, sustaining the livelihoods of approximately 54.6 per cent of the population. A significant characteristic of Indian agriculture is that around 70 per cent of the crops are rainfed, indicating that only 30 per cent of the cultivable land is irrigated. In the state of Maharashtra, the irrigation coverage is notably low, at just 13 per cent. Nevertheless, the expansion of irrigated land, coupled with the introduction of shorter-duration crop varieties, presents an opportunity to enhance cropping intensity through effective cropping sequences. Farmers are inclined to cultivate crops that entail minimal risk while offering substantial profits. Additionally, there is a desire among farmers for their family members to secure full-time employment on their farms year-round. Within the irrigated land of Maharashtra, a significant portion is dedicated to sugarcane, which is a vital cash crop for the state.

In the agricultural year 2022-23, sugarcane was cultivated over an area of 58.28 lakh hectares, yielding 33.7 million tons with a productivity rate of 81.93 tons per hectare. Notably, Western Maharashtra accounts for 70 per cent of the total area and 73 per cent of the total production of sugarcane in the state for the same period (Anonymous, 2022).

Human labor is the most significant input in sugarcane cultivation. Farmers aspire to cultivate this crop with minimum risk while achieving substantial financial returns. Simultaneously, they hope to ensure that their family members are employed year-round on their own farms.

Sugar industry is the second largest agro-based industry in India next only to textiles. Sugarcane is being considered as not merely a sugar-containing crop since it is increasingly assuming the status of energy crop. In India, about more than 50 million farmers, their dependents and a large number of agricultural labourers are involved in sugarcane cultivation, harvesting and ancillary activities constituting 7.5 per cent of the rural population and many workers are employed indirectly in processing. (Khushdeep, et al., 2007). as the cane is supplied to sugar industries, where various products from its juice are prepared by using a series of industry. The by-products from sugarcane further require some form of industry. Only a fraction of its production is used in small scale industry for making local 'Khandsari' and 'gur'. Sugarcane's products like sugar and fermented products are very important in making and preserving various kind of medicines like syrups, liquids, capsules etc. Sugarcane provides a juice, which is used. for making white sugar and jaggery (gur) and many by-products like bagasse and molasses. Bagasse is used as a fuel for production of fiber boards, papers, plastics and furfural. Molasses is used in distilleries for the manufacture of ethyl alcohol, butyl alcohol, citric acid etc. Rum is the best potable spirit made from molasses. Molasses, also, is used as an additive to feeds for livestock. Green tops of cane are a good source of fodder for cattle. Its remains are good manure in alkaline and saline soils.

Maharashtra has different sugarcane productivity zone according to soil, climate and recovery of sugar. Recovery of sugar ranges from 10

to 12 per cent. Different sugarcane producing zones of Maharashtra are as follows-

High recovery and medium productivity zone (south area) Kolhapur, Sangli and Satara (11-11.5% recovery).

Medium recovery and high productivity zone (central zone) North Satara, Pune. Solapur, Nashik and Ahmednagar district (10-11% recovery).

Low recovery and low productivity zone (North East Area) Khandesh. Marathwada and Vidarbha region (below 10% recovery).

Amongst the various cash crops grown, sugarcane is of prime importance in Maharashtra state. Though there are fluctuations in area and production from year to year, there is no substitute for sugarcane. Sugarcane is grown in three seasons. The plantation done in July-August is called 'Adsali' and required 17-18 months duration while the one planted in October - November is known as 'pre-seasonal' which is of 14-15 months duration. Plantation done in the month of January - February is called 'Suru' and required 12 months of its maturity.

The planting of sugarcane in Yavatmal district is done in Two season either in the month of October - November called pre-seasonal cultivation or in the month of January - February called seasonal (Suru) cultivation. After the harvesting of first cultivation, the cane growers take Ratoon crop. But in Yavatmal, the farmers usually favours the Suru cultivation because of its comparatively short duration and requirement of less number of irrigations as compared to pre-seasonal crop. As such it is felt necessary to study the economics of sugarcane plantation in Yavatmal district.

Some important varieties of sugarcane crop are Co 86032, Co 8005, Co 15012, Co 94012, Co 92005, Co 7219, MS 10001, CoM 9057, CoM 0265, CoC 671, CoVSI 434, CoVSI 03102 etc.

Advantages and disadvantages:**Pre-Seasonal Sugarcane:**

Advantages: -1) Higher Yield: Generally, pre-seasonal varieties can produce higher sugarcane yields. 2) Better Sugar Quality: Often results in higher sucrose content, making it more valuable for processing.

Disadvantages: -1) Weather Vulnerability: More susceptible to adverse weather conditions like drought or unseasonal rains. 2) May require more precise management in terms of irrigation and nutrient application. 3) Less varieties are available that can thrive in pre-seasonal conditions.

Suru Sugarcane:

Advantages: -More tolerant to varying environmental conditions, making it suitable for diverse climates. 2) Can grow well over a more extended period, allowing for better soil nutrient utilization. 3) Often requires less intensive management and inputs compared to pre-seasonal varieties.

Disadvantages: -1) Generally produces lower overall yields compared to pre-seasonal sugarcane. 2) May have lower sucrose content, impacting profitability for processors. 3) Harvesting takes place later in the season, which may coincide with lower market prices.

World scenario of sugarcane production:

In the year 2023-24, Brazil ranks first in both respect of area and production with area of 10042.19 thousand hectare and production of 752.9 million tonnes. India ranks second in both with area of 58.85 lakh hectare and production of 421.02 MT next to Brazil. Brazil being largest producer of sugarcane ranks first in production followed by India, China, Thailand and Pakistan. Brazil, India, Thailand, China, Pakistan, Mexico, Colombia, Australia, Indonesia, Guatemala are the top ten countries of sugarcane production. (Source: Directorate Of Economics and Statistics)

State wise area, production and productivity of sugarcane production:

In the year 2023-24, the area, production and yield of sugarcane in India was 57.40 lakh hectares, 453.16 Million tonnes and 82.255 Tonnes/ha, respectively.

In the 2023-24 agricultural year, Uttar Pradesh leads India in sugarcane cultivation, occupying an area of 26.53 lakh hectares and yielding a production of 215.81 million tonnes. Following closely, Maharashtra holds the second position with an area of 14.37 lakh hectares and a production of 112.09 million tonnes. Notably, Tamil Nadu excels in productivity, achieving 105.00 tonnes per hectare. In India major sugarcane growing states were Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Gujarat, Bihar and Tamilnadu. (Source: Directorate of Economics and Statistics)

District wise scenario of sugarcane in Maharashtra

In the year 2023-24, Kolhapur district ranks first in respect of area and second in production with area of 140484 hundred hectare and production 11384118 hundred tonnes. But Pune district first in production 11385547 hundred tonnes. But Satara and Sangli districts has highest average yield of 106.87 kg/ha followed by pune district with average yield of 103.26 kg/ha. (Source: Directorate of economics and statistic.) Area of sugarcane cultivation in Yavatmal district is 12000 ha. with the production of 763560 tonnes and productivity of 63.63 t/ha. (Source : Directorate of Economics and Statistics).

Importance of study:

The prices of inputs *viz.*, planting material, fertilizers, insecticides and labour wages are showing an increasing trend over a period of time. Moreover, farmers do not use the recommended levels of inputs. In the past, several attempts have been made to study the resource use levels, costs and returns structure of sugarcane crop. However, there is a need to examine the resource use, productivity, costs and returns of this crop

SN	Name of tahsils	Name of village	Pre-seasonal sugarcane	Suru sugarcane
1	Pusad	Bhojla	10	10
		Shelu	10	10
2	Umarkhed	Uti	10	10
		Amboda	10	10
3	Mahagon	Gajegaon	10	10
		Dhanki	10	10
		Total	60	60

collection of data

A schedule was designed for data collection by keeping in view the objectives of the study, the data pertains for the year 2022-23 and was collected through personal interview method from selected farmers. Data pertaining to cropping pattern, input utilization, cost of cultivation and returns were collected from the selected growers and other relevant information related to sugarcane was collected through a survey method with the help of pre-tested schedule.

Analysis of data

To accomplish the objectives of present study Simple tabular analysis was used. The economics of pre-seasonal and suru sugarcane cultivation was calculated by using standard cost concept

In the present study, the rent paid for leased inland was zero, as none of sample farmers took land on lease basis. Hence Cost A₁ and Cost A₂ are

from time to time in order to know its economic viability. The evolution of improved technology in production of sugarcane provided new alternatives for various adjustments in allocation the available resources. Many recent studies have shown that there were imperfections in resource allocations patterns of the sugarcane fa. In view of this, the present study entitled, "Comparative economics of pre-seasonal and suru sugarcane cultivation in Yavatmal district" is taken up to examine the costs and return s, resource use efficiency, to asses the decomposition of production inputs and to identify the constraints in adoption of sugarcane production technologies in Yavatmal district of Vidharbha region. Keeping this in the view, the present study have been undertaken with the following objectives.

Methodology

In any scientific study, it is necessary for investigator to get acquainted with the method of conducting research. He should also follow appropriate steps in carrying out research to get desired results. In the field of research in agriculture economics, the steps involved are selection of research topic, formulation of objectives, nature and sources of data to be collected, deciding methods of collection of data and analysis of data. The utility of any study depends upon the reliability of the data collected and the soundness of the material and methods used in the study. This chapter deals with the selection of area, selection of tahsils and villages, selection of sample, preparation of schedule, collection of data and analysis and interpretation of data.

Selection of area:

The present study was undertaken in Yavatmal district of Vidarbha region. The district was selected purposively. The data pertained for the year 2022-23.

3Selection of tahsils and villages

Out of the total sixteen tahsils in the Yavatmal district, three tahsils namely Pusad, Umbarkhed and Mahgaon were selected based on the highest area under cultivation in the district. From each tahsil, 2 villages were selected for present study.

A multistage random sampling technique was adopted for the selection of sample. The three tahsils was selected from Yavatmal District That is umerkhed, Mahagaon ,Pusad. Two villages from each tahsils and 10 farmers from each village for pre-sesonal and suru sugarcane cultivation was selected for present study. As such total 120 farmers was selected.

similar and simply called C. As Cost A and only Cost C₂ was estimated and presented as cost of cultivation in the result.

- Gross return per rupee of investment = $\frac{\text{Gross return}}{\text{Total investment}}$
- Cost of production tone = $\frac{\text{Total cost} - \text{value of by produce}}{\text{Yield (tone/Ha)}}$
- Gross return per tone = $\frac{\text{Gross return (Rs.Ha)}}{\text{Yield (tone/Ha)}}$

Result and discussion

Cost of cultivation of sugarcane

The share of each item's in total cost that is required for cost savings is provided. The basic cost ideas— Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂ and Cost C₃, were used to determine the cost. Various cost concepts have varied research utilities. An attempt has been made to

estimate the costs of sugarcane crops in the research area, which are shown in the tables that follow.

Table 1. Per hectare input utilization pattern of selected farmers

Particulars	Pre-seasonal sugarcane		Suru sugarcane	
	Physical unit		Physical unit	
sugarcane sett (Tone)	8.94		9.58	
Manure (Tone)	3.93		5.01	
N Kg	173.37		181.38	
P Kg	101.94		102.02	
K Kg	87.77		85.98	
Hired human labour (Days)	116.89		115.89	
Family labour (Days)	26.44		28.23	
Machine hours (Hr.)	13.77		14.76	

It is observed from Table 1. that input utilization of pre-seasonal sugarcane is less than that in suru sugarcane cultivation. In case of pre-seasonal sugarcane, the requirement of sugarcane setts was 8.94 tone/ha, where as in suru sugarcane it was 9.58 tone/ha. The use of N, P, K, by pre-seasonal sugarcane cultivator were 173.37, 101.94, 87.77 kg/ha where as in case of suru sugarcane it was 181.38, 102.02, 85.98 kg/ha.

The hired human labour requirements are more in case of pre-seasonal sugarcane and less in case of suru sugarcane cultivation. The more family labour work in case of suru sugarcane as compared to pre-seasonal sugarcane cultivation.

Cost of cultivation of pre-seasonal sugarcane grown by farmers is presented in Table 2.

Table 5.2.2 Cost of cultivation of pre-seasonal sugarcane (Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Input/ ha.	Cost/ Unit of input	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '
1	2	3			4	5	6
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	44.43	373.73	16604.82	6.98
		Female	Days	72.46	284.17	20590.76	8.66
		Total	Days	116.89		37195.58	15.63
2	Bullock Labour	Total	Days	0.14	857.50	120.05	0.05
3	Machine charges	Hired	Hrs	13.77	733.47	10099.9	4.25
4	Sugarcane sett	Tone	Tone	8.94	3258.12	29127.6	12.24
5	Manure	Tone	Qtls.	3.93	2148.11	8442.06	3.55
6	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	173.37	35.16	6094.93	2.56
		P	Kg.	95.87	37.33	3578.82	1.50
		K	Kg.	79.77	39.13	3126.18	1.31
		Total	Kg.	349.01		12799.93	5.38
7	Irrigation charges.	(Rs.)				5026.79	2.11
8	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				575.61	0.24
9	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				625.56	0.26
10	Plant Protection	(Rs.)				8995.24	3.78
11	Working Capital (1to10)	(Rs.)				113008.32	47.50
12	Interest on working Cap.	(Rs.)				8475.62	3.56
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)				5605.27	2.36
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				138.00	0.06
15	COST " A ₁ " (Item 11 to 14)	(Rs.)				127227.21	53.48
16	Rent paid for Leased in land					0.00	0.00
17	COST " A ₂ " (Item 15 to 16)					127227.21	53.48
18	Int. on Fix. Cap. @ 10%					8687.30	3.65
19	COST " B ₁ " (Item 15 to 18)					135914.51	57.13
20	Rental Value of owned Land	(Rs.)				71770.57	30.17
21	COST " B ₂ " (Item 19 to 20)					207685.09	87.30
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	17.23	355.22	6120.56	2.57
		Female	Days	9.22	267.55	2466.85	1.04
		Total	Days	26.44		8587.41	3.61
23	Cost " C ₁ " (Item 19 to 22)	(Rs.)				144501.92	60.74
24	Cost " C ₂ " (Item 21 to 22)	(Rs.)				216272.50	90.91
25	10% Cost " C ₂ "					21627.25	9.09
26	Cost " C ₃ " (Item 24 to 25)					237899.75	100.00
27	Yield per hectare main produce	(Tone)		151.84	2601.48	395009.38	
28	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Tone)		30.37	1199.94	36442.06	
29	Value of total produce	(Rs.)		182.21	2367.88	431451.44	

30	Per tone cost of Prod.	(Rs.)				1558.87
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It is revealed from Table 2 that the per hectare cost of cultivation of pre-seasonal sugarcane at Cost A₁, Cost A₂, Cost B₁, Cost B₂, Cost C₁, Cost C₂ and Cost C₃ were Rs.127227.21, Rs.127227.21, Rs.135914.51, Rs.207685.09, Rs.144501.92, Rs.216272.50 and Rs.237899.75 respectively. The major share of cost of cultivation goes towards Cost 'A₁' i.e 53.48 per cent. In Cost A₁ share of hired human labour 15.63 per cent, sugarcane sett 12.24 per cent, fertilizer 5.38 per cent and family human labour 3.61 per cent share to Cost C₃ respectively. It indicate that, all the above inputs are cash inputs for which farmers required to pay immediately from his pocket. The per ha yield was 151.84 Tone and per ha by produce yield was 30.37 Tone and gross return obtained was Rs. 431451.44 The per tone cost of production of pre-seasonal sugarcane was Rs. 1558.87.

Table 3 Cost of cultivation of suru sugarcane

(Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	Item	Unit		Input/ ha.	Cost/ Unit of input	Total Cost per ha.	% to Cost 'C ₃ '
1	2	3			4	5	6
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	Days	41.96	341.94	14347.81	6.27
		Female	Days	73.93	270.07	19965.91	8.72
		Total	Days	115.89		34313.72	14.98
2	Bullock Labour	Total	Days	0.17	903.35	153.57	0.07
3	Machine charges	Hired	Hrs	14.76	675.20	9965.91	4.35
4	Sugarcane sett	Tone	Tone	9.58	3412.52	32691.96	14.28
5	Manure	Tone	Qtls.	5.01	2283.91	11442.37	5.00
6	Fertilizer	N	Kg.	181.38	35.15	6375.77	2.78
		P	Kg.	95.96	37.26	3575.46	1.56
		K	Kg.	77.98	39.12	3045.12	1.33
		Total	Kg.	355.32		12996.35	5.68
7	Irrigation charges.	(Rs.)				5067.37	2.21
8	Incidental charges	(Rs.)				653.77	0.29
9	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)				730.51	0.32
10	Plant Protection	(Rs.)				9726.87	4.25
11	Working Capital (1to10)	(Rs.)				117742.40	51.42
12	Interest on working Cap.	(Rs.)				7064.54	3.09
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)				4798.53	2.10
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)				138.00	0.06
15	COST " A ₁ " (Item 11 to 14)	(Rs.)				129743.47	56.66
16	Rent paid for Leased in land					0.00	0.00
17	COST " A ₂ " (Item 15 to 16)					129743.47	56.66
18	Int. on Fix. Cap. @ 10%					5348.54	2.34
19	COST " B ₁ " (Item 15 to 18)					135092.01	58.99
20	Rental Value of owned Land	(Rs.)				64120.65	28.00
21	COST " B ₂ " (Item 19 to 20)					199212.66	87.00
22	Family Human Labour	Male	Days	18.15	345.70	6274.59	2.74
		Female	Days	10.8	248.84	2687.5	1.17
		Total	Days	28.23		8962.09	3.91
23	Cost " C ₁ " (Item 19 to 22)	(Rs.)				144054.10	62.91
24	Cost " C ₂ " (Item 21 to 22)	(Rs.)				208174.75	90.91
25	10% Cost " C ₂ "					20817.47	9.09
26	Cost " C ₃ " (Item 24 to 25)					228992.22	100.00
27	Yield per main produce hectare	(Tone)		135.12	2613.40	353123.62	
28	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Tone)		27.02	1200.15	32428.25	
29	Value of total produce	(Rs.)		162.14	2377.89	385551.87	
30	Per tone cost of Prod.	(Rs.)				1685.85	

Table 4 Comparative economic analysis of pre-seasonal and suru sugarcane

(Rs/ha)

Sr. No.	Item		Pre-seasonal	Suru
1	2		3	4
1	Hired Human Labour	Male	16604.82	14347.81

		Female	20590.76	19965.91
		Total	37195.58	34313.72
2	Bullock Labour	Total	120.05	153.57
3	Machine charges	Hired	10099.9	9965.91
4	Sugaercane sett	Tone	29127.6	32691.96
5	Manure	Tone	8442.06	11442.37
6	Fertilizer	N	6094.93	6375.77
		P	3578.89	3575.93
		K	3125.91	3036.44
		Total	12799.73	12988.14
7	Irrigation charges.	(Rs.)	5026.79	5067.37
8	Incidental charges	(Rs.)	575.61	653.77
9	Repairing Charges	(Rs.)	625.76	738.72
10	Plant Protection	(Rs.)	8995.24	9726.87
11	Working Capital (1to10)	(Rs.)	113008.32	117742.40
12	Interest on working Cap.	(Rs.)	8475.62	7064.54
13	Depreciation	(Rs.)	5605.27	4798.53
14	Land Revenue	(Rs.)	138.00	138.00
15	COST " A ₁ " (Item 11 to 14)	(Rs.)	127227.21	129743.47
16	Rent paid for Leased in land		0.00	0.00
17	COST " A ₂ " (Item 15 to 16)		127227.21	129743.47
18	Int. on Fix. Cap. @ 10%		8687.30	5348.54
19	COST " B ₁ " (Item 15 to 18)		135914.51	135092.01
20	Rental Value of owned Land	(Rs.)	71770.57	64120.65
21	COST " B ₂ " (Item 19 to 20)		207685.09	199212.66
22	Family Human Labour	Male	6120.56	6274.59
		Female	2466.85	2687.5
		Total	8587.41	8962.09
23	Cost " C ₁ " (Item 19 to 22)	(Rs.)	144501.92	144054.10
24	Cost " C ₂ " (Item 21 to 22)	(Rs.)	216272.50	208174.75
25	10% Cost " C ₂ "		21627.25	20817.47
26	Cost " C ₃ " (Item 24 to 25)		237899.75	228992.22
27	Yield per main produce hectare	(Tone)	395009.38	353123.62
28	Value of By-produce/ha.	(Tone)	36442.06	32428.25
29	Value of total produce	(Rs.)	431451.44	385551.87
30	Per tone cost of Prod.	(Rs.)	1558.87	1685.85

It could be seen from Table 4 the working capital required for cultivating suru sugarcane is higher (Rs.117742.40) than pre-seasonal sugarcane cultivation (Rs.113008.32). The cost A₁, was highest in suru sugarcane than pre-seasonal sugarcane and the cost B₁, B₂, C₁ and C₂ were highest in pre-seasonal sugarcane cultivation than suru sugarcane cultivation.

Table No: 5 Cost and returns from pre-seasonal and suru sugarcane.
(Rs/tonne)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Type of cultivation	
		Pre-seasonal	Suru
1	Yield (Tone)	182.21	162.14
2	Value Main Produce	395009.38	353123.62
	By Produce	36442.06	32428.25
3	Total Produce	431451.44	385551.87
4	Total Cost		
	Cost A ₁	127227.214	129743.474
	Cost A ₂	127227.214	129743.474
	Cost B ₁	135914.514	135092.014
	Cost B ₂	207685.09	199212.66
	Cost C ₁	144501.924	144054.104
	Cost C ₂	216387.50	208289.75
5	Cost C ₃	238026.25	229118.72
	Net Return Over		
	Cost A ₁	304224.23	255808.40

The value of total produce was also higher in pre-seasonal sugarcane (Rs.431451.44) than suru sugarcane cultivation (Rs.385551.87). The per tone cost of production was higher (1685.85) in suru sugarcane cultivation than pre-seasonal sugarcane (1558.87).

	Cost A ₂	304224.23	255808.40
	Cost B ₁	295536.93	250459.86
	Cost B ₂	223766.35	186339.21
	Cost C ₁	144501.92	144054.10
	Cost C ₂	216272.50	208174.75
	Cost C ₃	237899.75	228992.22
6	Input Output ratio at		
	Cost A ₁	3.39	2.97
	Cost A ₂	3.39	2.97
	Cost B ₁	3.17	2.85
	Cost B ₂	2.08	1.94
	Cost C ₁	2.99	2.68
	Cost C ₂	1.99	1.85
	Cost C ₃	1.81	1.68

It is revealed from the Table 5 that, the yield per hectare realized in pre-seasonal sugarcane was 182.21 tones. The yield realized by suru sugarcane was 162.14 tones per hectare. The per hectare cost A₁ was more for suru sugarcane cultivation than in pre-seasonal sugarcane cultivation and cost B₁ and cost C₂ for pre-seasonal sugarcane were more when compared to that in suru sugarcane. For example, Cost C₂ was more by about Rs.8097.75/- for pre-seasonal sugarcane when compared to that in suru sugarcane. The per hectare gross returns realized for pre-seasonal sugarcane growers and suru sugarcane growers were Rs. 431451.44 and Rs. 385551.87 respectively. The net returns (returns over Cost C₂) were Rs. 216272.50/- for pre-seasonal sugarcane and Rs.208174.75/- for suru sugarcane. The highest input output ratio at cost 'C₃' was recorded for pre-seasonal sugarcane growers i.e. 1:1.81 and for suru sugarcane it was recorded as 1:1.68.

The input output ratio which is an indicator of economic efficiency in crop production for the crop and other discussion indicated that pre-seasonal sugarcane cultivation registered a good input output ratio 1:1.81 means this is profitable method of cultivation.

Conclusions

The per hectare cost of cultivation of pre-seasonal sugarcane was Rs.237899.75/- and for suru sugarcane was Rs.228992.22/-The highest input – output ratio at C₂ was recorded for pre-seasonal sugarcane i.e. 1:1.99 and for suru sugarcane was 1:1.85.Farmers growing pre-seasonal sugarcane obtained higher output per hectare than that of suru sugarcane.

Refernces

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